

CONTENT OF CREATE THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF A
TRANSLATOR IN TRAINING

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7481783>

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Annotation: *In the process of teaching translation, not the methods of translating the used educational material (text, utterance, word) should be studied, but methods for solving typical translation problems and the strategy for finding individual creative solutions. In this sense, teaching translation involves the ability to single out typical translation tasks in the training material and formulate general principles and particular methods for solving them. In different types of translation, both general principles and techniques, as well as specific methods for each type, can be applied.*

Key words: *Systematic, translation as communication, the characteristic of the scientific, scientific-technical style, literary scientific-technical style.scientific-technical style.*

The nature of interlingual communication predetermines the fundamental multiplicity of translation options for the same segments of the original. In this regard, in the learning process, students are not tasked with creating the only correct (or optimal) translation of the proposed text. At the same time, the learning process includes a critical assessment of educational translations and the rejection of unacceptable options.

The content of translation training is largely determined by the knowledge, skills and abilities that are necessary to create the professional competence of a translator in trainees.

Let us first try to briefly characterize the knowledge and skills that make up the main content of training. At the same time, it should be borne in mind that there is a close relationship between them and many skills can only be created on the basis of relevant knowledge. In the course of training, the future translator should acquire, in general, the following knowledge:

- get an idea about the main stages of the history of translation and the features of translation activity in the modern world;
- get an idea about the concept of translatability, non-identity of the content of the original and translation, the principle of ensuring minimal losses;
- get an idea of the pragmatic aspects of translation and the main ways of pragmatic adaptation of translation;
- get an idea about the classification of translations and different types of translation strategy;
- to study the main models of translation and translation transformations and how to use them in the analysis of the translation process and its results;
- get an idea of the grammatical and stylistic aspects of the translation.

All this knowledge is communicated to students both at special lectures and seminars, and during practical classes. At the same time, it is very important that students clearly see the connection between the acquired knowledge and translation practice, their necessity for solving specific problems of translation.

A professional translator needs to have an idea of the socio-historical role of translation and the main stages in the development of translation activity. He should be aware of the enormous contribution of translators to the formation of the national language, literature and culture of peoples, the role of translation in international contacts in the field of diplomacy, politics, trade, science and technology. All this knowledge allows future translators to realize the complexity

and importance of their profession, to get acquainted with the material and organizational aspects of the work of a translator.

The understanding of the essence of translation activity is based on the understanding of translation as one of the main ways of language mediation, which provides the possibility of communication between people who speak different languages. Future translators study the main components of interlingual communication and the factors influencing its implementation, get acquainted with various types of linguistic mediation and single out translation as a way to create a text in the target language intended to fully functionally replace the original text. Students get acquainted with the basic requirements that a translation must satisfy in order to successfully fulfill its communicative function: the requirement of equivalence, that is, the necessary and sufficient degree of closeness to the original, and the requirement of adequacy, that is, the ability to perform the pragmatic task for which the translation was made, to produce desired communication effect. Translation is one of the types of human activity. The translator satisfies the social need by his activity.

Translation is the process of converting text in one language into text in another language while keeping the content relatively unchanged.

Translation should be taught as a special academic discipline, and mastering the ability to translate is not the prerogative of especially gifted people. This position is now generally recognized, and in all educational institutions that train translators, students are offered classes in the theory and practice of translation. The methodology of teaching translation is based on the belief that a person has the ability to translate genetically, as well as the ability to master languages.

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